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Relational Model for Robotic Semantic Navigation in Indoor Environments

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Abstract The emergence of service robots in our environment raises the need to find systems that help the robots in the task of managing the information from human environments. A semantic model of the environment provides the robot with a representation closer to the human perception, and it improves its human-robot communication system. In addition, a semantic model will improve the capabilities of the robot to carry out high level navigation tasks. This paper presents a semantic relational model that includes conceptual and physical representation of objects and places, utilities of the objects, and semantic relation among objects and places. This model allows the robot to manage the environment and to make queries about the environment in order to do plans for navigation tasks. In addition, this model has several advantages such as conceptual simplicity and flexibility of adaptation to different environments. To test the performance of the proposed semantic model, the output for the semantic inference system is associate to the geometric and topological information of objects and places in order to do the navigation tasks.

Keywords Robot navigation · environment representation · semantic modelling · semantic inference

1 Introduction

To help service robots to work in human environments they need high level perception and behavioral mechanisms closer to human models of perception

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and reasoning. Ioannis Kostavelis et al. ensure in [23] that the ability of mobile robots to sense is decisive for their applicability to everyday activities. Robots that are provided with semantic models of the environments where they operate have a larger decision autonomy, and become more robust and more efficient. Therefore, in mobile robot navigation, the so-called semantic maps have already been used to improve path planning methods [16].

Semantic navigation is considered as a navigation system that takes into account semantic information to model the environment. This information and the relationships between the concepts are applied in tasks such as robot location, mapping, exploration and path planning. A comprehensive overview of the existing navigation techniques can be found in [39]. Something to be considered is that this navigation system is usually supported by the definition of an ontology [30].

In this work, semantic navigation is supported by a relational representation of the environment in which an ontology describes relations between concepts, and these concepts are part of a conceptual hierarchy linked to a spatial hierarchy. In our system the kinds of rooms are related to the objects they contain. These objects are related to their usefulness, characteristics and interactions with other objects. In this way the rooms may be also related to a utility. For example, if a place contains objects used to work, it is deduced that the place is a good destination for someone who wants to work. In addition, objects located in a room, are semantically as the room. A room containing a stove and a refrigerator is labeled as kitchen. It also gives the system the ability to know what objects can be in a room. If a place is labeled as kitchen, it may contain a stove and a refrigerator.

All these concepts are used to classify the place where objects are located. That information is used to reach a given location to meet a specific target. User may give orders such as *go to the kitchen* or I want to work now. A reasoning module uses information stored in a database to figure out which room corresponds to the kitchen (ie, the objects contained in that room correspond with the objects usually contained in a kitchen), in the first instance. In the second case, the robot leads the user to an office (this is because the reasoning module deduces that the usefulness of a computer is working and computers are in offices). Therefore, the robot can find places or rooms semantically related to the target, using the reasoning module. This module includes several relationships between concepts related to the environment that will be described in the following sections. When the user indicates to the system that he wants to go to a destination, the reasoning module deduces the physical locations where that destination can be reached. To do this, it uses a reasoner module. The reasoner implemented in this work uses a relational database which contains both the ontology proposed as well as the environment information. However, the reasoning module can be implemented using other inference systems. This possibility has been considered in the design stage and reasoning class module implements an interface to communicate with a generic inference system. In this way the reasoner can be changed without affecting the rest of the navigation system. So, in the implemented system, the reasoning module

makes a cross-search against the database using the field provided by the user. Because the tables are related according to the design of the ontology, the results are all items that can be destinations related to the user's request. The reasoning module maintains a fixed pattern of behavior. This module gets the information provided by the reasoner and it decides what is the best place to reach the target user, based on what it has been received. In this process it is likely that the reasoning module carries out multiple queries to the reasoner.

Semantic information of the model is given a priori, but it is contemplated that information can be not complete or that additional information can be added to the system from other databases or through user interaction.

2 Related works

In recent years, there is a growing interest on semantic knowledge applied in mobile robots navigation. Semantic navigation presents an step forward with respect to robotic navigation based on metric maps [6], topological maps [18], or hybrid maps [29]. Semantic information constitutes a better solution for interaction with humans [24]. In [22], these concepts are applied in order to understand natural language interactions when a person requests a robot to find a new object and the robot must look for that object in the environment.

The first issue to deal with is how to represent knowledge. Ontologies can be seen as one of the best ways of obtaining this representation [38]. In addition, hierarchies can be established where the highest levels of abstraction define its semantic interpretation. This knowledge is considered for the creation of semantic maps. In [31] they take into account all the information sources that have been published. Moreover, they combine information about the existence of objects in a room, landmarks or signs, the topological structure, room appearance and size, the space geometry and the data provided by an interaction with human users. The ontology is coded based on [10] and [19]. The authors of [19] presented an integrated approach for creating conceptual representations based on multiple maps at different levels of abstraction. They include a laser sensor, a camera and a system for spoken interaction. They provide a high level of human-robot communication and conceptual representation. All they are supported by a wide literature on localization, mapping and places classification as it is explained in [15], [17], [4] [20], [33] or [2].

In [10] the rules defining the ontology have to be hand-coded by the user. In the proposed work rules are included in the proposed relational model. In the case a manual insertion of knowledge is required, the user only needs to add data to the model and, based on the ontology representation, relations among data are implicitly established. For instance, if a new room type is added, it is only necessary to add it to the model and to add the objects which it may contain.

The work in [19] is based on the idea that humans partially adopt a hierarchical representation of spatial organization and a categorization of the spatial structures. Authors in this paper design a spatial representation divided

in different abstraction levels. Several ways of acquiring knowledge, common to other works, are proposed in [19]: Acquired knowledge (with its sensors), Confirmed knowledge (by an user), Innate conceptual knowledge (pre-set in the T-Box) and inferred knowledge.

There are several mechanism to label and to identify a region of space. In [41], the authors try to differentiate areas based on the usefulness of objects that are found. A Naive Bayes Classifier is employed, as in [32], to infer the place identification, in order to better group and create a set that represents an area. With this classification method, effectiveness is increased, as it is described in [37]. In the same line, [3] a semantic place classification of indoor using boosting is used. In [22] the authors also rely on probabilistic methods based on Naive Bayes for places classification and to obtain the probabilities of objects location. Relations between object-object and objet-scenario are used to predict the location of a variety of objects and scenarios. More recently there is an important paper [40] that also employs Bayesian approach for semantic mapping. The authors combine a semantic, topological and geometric mapping space and objects relating nodes. The location of the robot is performed with recognition methods places.

Several works are based on object recognition for environment labeling objects such as [35], [34] or [25] and for places [2],[26]. The development of a system of active visual search [1] must also be mentioned, it combines semantic hints to guide the process of object searching.

3 Modeling the Environment

Robotic navigation systems require a way of modeling and interpreting the environment. In the case of semantic navigation, a large amount of information related to the environment and to the objects contained can be extracted and represented. This representation requires an ontology to establish the concepts and the links of the objects in the environment.

Many works depend on a reasoning engine where rules and facts are included. Galindo, in this way, uses a representation of knowledge called LOOM [9] and a system called NeoClassic [10]. As an alternative, in this work, a relational model is proposed. Some advantages that will be discussed in this paper are obtained. Using reasoning engines rules must change from one environment to another. With our system only the environment information changes. This and other advantages will be Discussed in next paragraph.

The proposed relational model makes easy to store the information in tables that can be managed by the inference engine of a database [8], in order to test it, as it is done in this work. A considerable advantage of using the system proposed in this work, is the capacity for changing the environment without alterations of the relational model. Using a reasoning engine, rules must be changed by programmers or an advanced IA when the environment (i.e.: office, house) is modified. But using the system described in this paper, is not necessary because the rules are substituted by relations. In [19] user

information may be added by a tour. However, the rules must be predefined, as in [10]. In our system the semantics of an environment can be changed from *home* to *office* for example, without knowledge representation of logical rules. This makes easier its use by a final user and avoids the time spent to define rules. The relations between entities are implicit in the database design and only introducing new data is necessary. In addition, this architecture also allows the robot to deduce new types of rooms, without creating new rules. The idea in [9] of keeping on one hand the abstract entities and on the other hand the physical objects perceived, both types of information related through links, remains in this architecture. These benefits are obtained whether conventional databases are used as though object oriented databases are used. In this work we have used conventional databases because it allows separate the object information that must be stored and the data that must not be saved, because defined classes had information that there was no need to store.

In the case that the robot identifies objects in a same room with a common utility, it can then deduced that it is located in a room where the robot could find more objects with related utilities. Therefore, new categories for rooms are autonomously created.

The objects and room identification also allow to detect possible inconsistencies. In [13] some methods of how to solve the situation are detailed. In our paper, one method to solve this is to find an object that catalogues the room. If the robot finds a stove in a room identified as living room, then it is also a kitchen. The incoherence is solved by cataloging that room as living room-kitchen, understanding that it is both things. If the object that defines the room cannot be found, that inconsistency must be stored and later the robot must decide how it should solve it. It is strange to find a refrigerator in a living room, but if it happens, the robot must keep the consistency by considering it as an exception.

Another advantage of the proposed relational model is that objects can be linked in an easy way to the topological and geometrical level of the navigation system, allowing the inclusion of geometrical information, and the relations of semantic information to nodes and edges of a topological graph.

3.1 Relational model representation

In order to shown the model representation, an entity-relationship diagram is shown in Fig 1. The conceptual objects and conceptual rooms are related to physical objects and physical rooms, following the idea proposed by other authors such as [19], joining the conceptual hierarchy and the spatial hierarchy. In addition, objects in a domestic environment are considered. This is reflected in other models of knowledge as the one used in [21]. They link objects with verbs by the *usedFor* relationship, as the *utility* relationship used in this work. This diagram collects the main aspects of the proposed semantic representation of the environment, in which places, objects and meanings are stored in tables. The proposed model is focused on the navigation task and is designed to be

Fig. 1 Database design for semantic navigation

as simple and complete as possible. Other more generic semantic knowledge models are similar to the model in [27] (figure 2). As may be seen in that work, a universal model requires managing events, resources, actors, contexts, etc. Other authors [42] are based on generic models and they adjust them (figure 3) for domestic environments. In this model the concepts are related by *is-a* relationships and it is considerably more complex than the proposed model in this paper which focuses on navigation task. For example, in our system everything the robot need to know about the dishwasher is that it is in the kitchen and it may contain a number of objects. And that is represented by the conceptual relationship between object (dishwasher) and the relationship between these conceptual objects would be stored into *interaction* table (the object dishwasher, the object dish and the relationship *contains* would be stored into *interaction* table, for example). The proposed model is used in a similar way to that depicted in Figure 3. If there are the appliance and dishwasher conceptual objects, the *is-a* relationship can be represented by the *interaction* relationship. And *is-a* is the kind of the interaction. In summary, the proposed model can be used to represent the desired complexity but also allows focusing on navigation (which is what is intended) and therefore simplify the model.

3.1.1 Conceptual elements and physical elements of the environment

This type of tables are those that arise when considering the four elements the robot must store : physical rooms (real locations sensorially perceived by the robot), conceptual rooms (the type of room the robot can recognize), physical objects (objects perceived by sensors) and conceptual objects (each object's semantic information that the robot must recognize). Therefore, being based on this description, the following tables exist:

Fig. 2 Generic knowledge model.

Fig. 3 Knowledge model.

ConceptualRoom: This table contains the information of the rooms understood as concepts. The table records are those corresponding to the concepts *kitchen*, *living room*, *dining room*, etc.

ConceptualObject: This table stores data related to objects abstractly defined and understood as concepts, for example, *Refrigerator*, *Sofa*, *Computer*, *Washing machine*, etc.

PhysicalRoom: This table corresponds to physical rooms (understood as locations, places in space, regions delimited by walls, having real coordinate, etc) by which the robot can move.

PhysicalObject: This table stores each real object that the sensors of the robot identify. This table records can be *Chair-1*, *Chair-2*, *Refrigerator-1*, etc.

Relating to these basic tables that represent the model, the following links that generate new tables exist because of the links of the type *many-to-many*: *ConceptualObjectRoom* (the relationship between *ConceptualRoom* and *ConceptualObject* gives as a result this table) and *PhysicalConceptualRoom* (the link between *ConceptualRoom* and *Physicalroom* produces this one).

3.1.2 Linking Conceptual elements and physical elements

In this work, among conceptual and physical elements some links have been defined. Among *PhysicalRooms* and *PhysicalObjects* there is a link that corresponds to the fact that a physical object is located in a single physical room. And a physical room may have an indeterminate amount of physical objects. This information is added to the table *PhysicalObject*. Some authors use relations to match symbolic information to environment elements, as [14] that uses correspondences between symbols and sensor data from physical objects.

Among *ConceptualObjects* and *PhysicalObjects* another link is found, due to the fact that each physical object corresponds to a single conceptual object. This information is also added to the table *PhysicalObject*.

3.1.3 Adding Semantic Information to the Objects

Figure 1 shows the diagram of the designed relational model. There are several tables that manage important information that can be used by the robot to find objects which have a relation with other objects. The idea is, that if the robot searches for an specific object in the environment which has no information about its localization, it can deduce with what other objects is linked to, by searching this new objects. For this purpose, the followings concepts have been considered:

Interaction: In this work, the possibilities of physical connections and relations between objects are defined as interaction. This table can handle any type of interaction, although tests have been performed with a limited number of them. The interactions taken into account are: *BE_A*, when an object is a subtype of another object; *IS_USED_WITH*, when an object is used with an object and *IS_INSIDE_OF*, when usually an object is inside another object.

Interactions allow the system to find objects that are related and that are in nearby locations. The type of interaction can be increased to endow the system more flexibility. This allows users in any culture to indicate what objects are related in this way, for any relation that causes two objects have a nearby location.

Utility: As artifacts made or modified by humans, all objects have one or more utilities. And the tendency is to group objects that have the same utility (or something related) in the same places. And also concepts are created regarding kinds of room depending on what they are used for. Utilities can be linked to affordance issues [36] in other stages.

Meaning: The actions or utilities that an object has, often are associated with a specific meaning by humans. The goal of the navigation may also be oriented to emotions that generate objects and places that give a private feeling, such as calm or fun. For example, *read* can be assigned to the meaning *quiet* but can be assigned to the meaning *fun* or *bored* meaning depending on the user or on the user context.

Characteristic: Objects definition can include features and properties to best define the concept or even differentiate them from others. For example, water may be cold, warm or hot. Therefore, it implies differences in location. Cold water may be found in the refrigerator or in a fountain, but hot water would come out from the tap. These characteristics have been taken into account for situations in which an object changes its purpose when it changes their properties.

This information about objects has been stored in tables too. With these tables the desired use level of the semantics of objects in the environment is achieved, in order to be able to search for them. For example, in the case of the utilities concepts, it can be mentioned that the *computer* is used to *work*. If the user requests to go to a place to work, the robot goes to the place where the computer is located.

With this relational database model, the semantic knowledge is obtained using simple queries without the need to define rules as it has been described in previous works [9] [10].

Thus, figures 4 and 5 show how the information would be organized in an environment that is being partially explored. Figure 4 shows the relationships between the information of room-3 that the robot knows. In this example, the room-3 is an office. The conceptual level is represented by the rectangular boxes and the physical level by ellipses. Relations between conceptual level concepts correspond to the ontological architecture. The semantic knowledge is manifested in the union of the conceptual hierarchy and spatial hierarchy. The information shown in this figure means that the printer is related to office, chair and computer. This is because they are objects that are in this kind of stay. In turn, these objects have relationships with other items or objects. The printer paper interacts with the object, the computer is used not only to work but also to watch movies. In turn, watching movies is related to the fun concept. The computer interacts with the printer because the printers are

Fig. 4 Example of relationships of concepts and physical elements of an environment partially explored

used with a computer. The chair serves to rest and sit, with actions that are related respectively with comfort and relaxing activity.

Noting figure 5, a broader spatial hierarchy section is provided, and the union of conceptual level is displayed with the elements of room-1. This stay has been linked to the kitchen concept, since two stoves, a refrigerator and a cupboard have been identified. This figure shows a type of relationships that were not in the previous figure and that are related to the characteristics of objects. Both the refrigerator and the sink are related to the concept water. But while the refrigerator contains only cold water, sink contains cold or hot water. And according to this feature of the water, the utility also changes.

The database contains the ontology information for the robot navigation system as well as the physical objects detected in the environment and the physical stays identified on the map. Considering the elements of the two previous figures, the tables contain the database information shown in figure 6.

4 Semantic information management

This section shows how the system using a relational model with the implicit knowledge in its design, has been implemented. The system has a topological navigator and the planner translates the semantic information in topological commands.

4.1 Obtaining semantic target

This architecture includes a class that defines the concept of *semantic position* as a contextual information unit related to the position of the robot, creating

Fig. 5 Example of relationships of concepts and physical elements of an environment partially explored II

an algorithm to locate the target, where the input of that algorithm is an object of the class *SemanticPosition*. The class in this architecture contains attributes that correspond to a room code (the target room in this case) and the object code (the target object in this case). It is therefore understood, that a position is obtained in relation to a semantic reference point, which can be either objects or rooms. A variable of the class *SemanticPosition* represents the target where the robot must go. Several different options depending on the information available in the database of the requested destination and the type of destination (object or room) can be given:

Unknown room. If the destination is an unknown room, the field of the room id of the object of the class *SemanticPosition* will still have void value. It is the case in which the room has not been explored. Then the navigation system will launch the corresponding semantic exploration routine and it tries to recognize the room, in this example, a kitchen.

Known room. If the target is a room, and if it has been explored, the variable target will have a value in the field of the room id corresponding to the physical room which is already known.

Known object in a known room. Another possibility is that the original target is an object, such as the refrigerator. In that case, after completing the function, the variable *SemanticTarget* of the class *SemanticPosition* will have

Fig. 6 Instance of the database environment partially explored.

the id of the specific object (refrigerator-1) and of the room where it is located (room-3), considering that the object has been explored and located.

Unknown object in a known room. If the robot does not have the previous information about an object in a room, for example, a refrigerator in the kitchen, the value of the object identifier would be void. Then, the robot would try to explore the room (room-3, kitchen) looking for the object (refrigerator).

Unknown object in an unknown room. If the object and the room are unknown (the kitchen has not been located), the robot will first explore looking for a room (kitchen). The conclusion that the robot must explore looking for a kitchen occurs both if the kitchen itself has been a requested target or if an object that may be found in the kitchen has been requested, such as the refrigerator.

An example To help understand the process of performance of this function is shown in figure 7, where the object to look for is a chair. There is an array of destinations that are being assorted in LIFO order because destinations are chained one after another in the system. This happens when the system detects that, to reach the first destination that has been received, the robot must reach others previously. These new destinations are added so they have priority over the first. In the example of locating an object (a Chair in figure

Fig. 7 Diagram that shows the possible actions of the function *TargetLocation* in an example of finding a chair

7), 5 possible outcomes A, B, C, D and E can be obtained. In A result, the chair was identified and therefore the room where the object was found was also identified. When the planner finds a situation of this type, it directly sends the event to the low level navigator (the topological) to go to that room and afterwards to that object. However, for results B, C and D, the variable *target* does not have information about any physical object, but it has information on the search for a conceptual object CHAIR and it also adds information of the physical room where the robot should go to find a chair.

Reasoning module that handles events destination request is implemented starting with algorithm 1. This algorithm is executed when a request destination is received and causes the destination vector to be updated. The pseudo-code corresponds to the state machine developed to manage the database. It can be noticed that the algorithm works in a recursive way.

In the case shown in the example of Figure 7, the function *searchForObject* is executed, that its pseudo-code is the algorithm 2. One observation to

Algorithm 1 Target obtention from semantic destination

Require: SemanticPosition *target* with the new target information.

```

1: if target is a conceptual room goal then
2:   getPhysicalRoomFromConceptualRoom(target)
3: else if target is an object goal then
4:   searchForObject(target)
5: else if target is an Action then
6:   searchForAction(target)
7: else if target is a subjective meaning then
8:   searchForMeaning(target)
9: else
10:  print error message
11: end if
12: return

```

note is that the system that manages the semantic navigation is disengaged from the part system that focuses on reasoning. This is seen in line 1, which shows that there is a global variable called *reasoner*. This variable implements an interface mode that allows us to replace the inference method creating a new class that also implements that interface and thereby redefines all methods with another tool or technology. In this paper, the reasoning is implemented with a relational database that contains the ontology defined. The navigation system also works if it is implemented with an inference engine, for example. In this case, what is needed is to extract information from which physical objects (spatial hierarchy) that correspond to the conceptual object (the conceptual hierarchy) being searched.

Algorithm 2 searchForObject destination

Require: SemanticPosition *target* with the new target information.

```

1: objectList = reasoner.getPhysicalObjectFromConcept(target.object.code, target.object.characteristic)

2: if objectList ≠ {} a object-not-discard exist then
3:   publish event to go to the first physical object from the list.
4:   return
5: else
6:   searchPossibleLocationFromAnObject(target)
7: end if
8: return

```

Following the execution sequence example, now it calls the function of the algorithm 3. Line 15 means that when the system has not found an object with a characteristic, it tries looking for a more generic object (same object without property) before the search fails.

In this example, the program flow proceeds to running the function *searchObjectsOrRooms*, since the locations list is not empty and line 4 of the algorithm 3 gets a call successfully. The pseudo-code for this function is the algorithm 4.

This work focuses on the reasoner module. When the system receives a request destination and the result is to search an unseen object or room, the

Algorithm 3 searchPossibleLocationFromAnObject**Require:** SemanticPosition *target* with the new target information.

```

1: locationList = reasoner.getPossibleLocationFromObject(target.object.code, target.object.characteristic)
2: searchSemanticProximity = false
3: if locationList ≠ {} then
4:   bool success = searchObjectsOrRooms(target.object.code, locationList)
5:   if !success then
6:     searchSemanticProximity = true
7:   end if
8: else
9:   searchSemanticProximity = true
10: end if
11: if searchSemanticProximity then
12:   bool result = searchBySemanticProximity(target)
13:   if result = OK then
14:     add new target in destination vector (target updated)
15:   else if target has characteristic then
16:     remove target.object.characteristic
17:     create new target and push on vector
18:     searchPossibleLocationFromAnObject(newtarget)
19:   else
20:     publish event to explore
21:   end if
22: end if
23: return

```

reasoner assigns the task to the explorer. If the request was go to a room, the explorer commands the robot wander until the sensors detect an object that identifies the requested room. If an object had been requested, the robot goes to the most probably place to find the object and there begins to wander until it finds it. In both cases there is a configurable timeout that stops the search and deemed to have failed.

4.2 Semantic identification of the room

Semantic information would be needed to identify the room from a vector of detected objects. There is a function in the system that deletes from the vector the objects already known, to only analyze those observed for the first time. For all new objects, it gets the room codes that the object returns with a query that returns a list of the types of room where the object can be found. If an object is found that its presence defines the room where it is located, then the list of room types will only have one element. For example, the stove is an object that can only be in the kitchen, so that room is a kitchen. If there is a stove in a room containing a sofa and a table it has been identified as *living room* and *dining room*. In this system, the same room can match an infinite number of types of room. If the result of the previous query does not return a single record, it is because the referred object is not discriminatory enough to be able to conclude any identification.

Algorithm 4 searchObjectsOrRooms

Require: String *code*, vector *list***Ensure:** bool, true if success

```

1: bool OK = true
2: bool continue = true
3: for all elements of list and continue = true do
4:   string object_code = element.object.code
5:   string room_code = element.room.code
6:   if object_code failed previously then
7:     OK = false
8:   end if
9:   if OK then
10:    continue = false
11:   end if
12: end for
13: if OK then
14:   if There is OBJECT then
15:     if There is ROOM then
16:       vectorobjects = reasoner.getPhysicalObjectFromConceptualObject(object_code)
17:       vectorrooms = reasoner.getPhysicalRoomsFromConceptualRoom(room_code)
18:       create newtarget and add it on destination vector
19:     else
20:       searchForAnObject(new SemanticPosition(object_code))
21:     end if
22:   else
23:     reasoner.getPhysicalRoomsFromConceptualRoom(room_code)
24:     create newtarget and add it on destination vector
25:   end if
26: end if
27: return OK

```

5 Adding information to the environment model

Several ways of adding the information to the environment model are contemplated :

***A priori* information:** At the beginning, the information of the environment is fulfilled by the user. Information of places and objects might not be complete and acquired in the future.

Adding information from the robot sensors: When navigating, robot can detect objects from the environment and it can add the information and relations to places and other objects. The sensory system works by adding several different systems object detection. We used previously works, for instance [7] and recently we have added the system that is described in [5]. These systems works detecting the shapes of the objects for detecting generic objetos and using descriptors to identify specific objects. Because of the difficulty that the typical object detection systems, sensory system also includes a marks and labels detection to identify the most difficult object to detect. This also works with objects detectors that have not been trained with a specific object. One of these systems for marks detecting that we use is within ARToolkit package.

The semantic navigation system has a explore module that is responsible for associating the objects perceived or identified rooms with geometric positions or topological nodes.

Adding information by interaction: When the robot needs more information, it is contemplated that robot interacts with human using speaking communication [28].

Adding information using knowledge databases: Robot can connect to knowledge database in order to complete meanings, utilities and other properties of objects and places in order to add relations.

6 Experiments

To carry out tests on this system, the inferring engine of a database has been chosen in order to demonstrate the functionality of the model. The database has been created with MySQL 5.5.43 for Ubuntu 12.04. The system has been created within a package ROS (indigo version) to which has been added libmysqlclient-dev dependency to access the database from code in C ++. In the experiments, geometrical destination from a request to a semantic target, starts from a hypothetical situation of a partially explored environment, with the information contained in the table 1, with semantics defined by the table 3 and deducted knowledge stored in table 2. To focus the tests on the system of reasoning, planning and communication with the low level navigation system, this partial environment information was manually introduced into the database.

On these tables, that represent the knowledge the robot has, the system effectiveness has been tested.

PhysicalObject		
Name	ConceptualName	RoomName
Chair-1	CHAIR	Room-1
Chair-2	CHAIR	Room-2
Chair-3	CHAIR	Room-3
Refrigerator-1	REFRIGERATOR	Room-1
Sofa-1	SOFA	Room-2
Desk-1	DESK	Room-3

Table 1 Content of the table PhysicalObject

ConceptualPhysicalRoom	
ConceptualName	PhysicalName
Room-1	KITCHEN
Room-2	LIVING ROOM
Room-3	OFFICE

Table 2 ConceptualPhysicalRoom

ConceptualObjectRoom	
RoomName	ObjectName
KITCHEN	STOVE
KITCHEN	REFRIGERATOR
KITCHEN	SINK
KITCHEN	WASHING MACHINE
KITCHEN	HEATER
LIVING ROOM	SOFA
LIVING ROOM	COFFEE TABLE
LIVING ROOM	CHAIR
LIVING ROOM	TV SET
LIVING ROOM	HEATER
LIVING ROOM	BOOKCASE
DINING ROOM	CHAIR
DINING ROOM	DINING TABLE
DINING ROOM	HEATER
OFFICE	HEATER
OFFICE	CHAIR
OFFICE	BOOKCASE
OFFICE	DESK
OFFICE	COMPUTER
BATHROOM	WASHBASIN
BATHROOM	TOILET
BATHROOM	HEATER

Table 3 Content of the table ConceptualObjectRoom

6.1 Physical rooms

This test tries to analyze the behavior of the planner when a conceptual room is requested to be found, corresponding with a known physical room. The test consisted of asking for the KITCHEN in the case where the robot knows that there is a room that is a kitchen. In this case, the system issues a command to go to room-1, which corresponds to the kitchen. Checking the table *Physical-ConceptualRoom*, it can be seen that if a query is raised asking for KITCHEN, the result is *room-1*. If the user asks again for the kitchen, the system searches for another one, not having more kitchens in the database, explore the rest of the rooms.

6.2 Physical objects

The test described in this section, evaluates the system performance when attempting to find a conceptual object where real objects have been observed. In the initial environment, there are three real objects of the CHAIR type. When asked for a Chair, the system identifies *Chair-1*, *Chair-2* and *Chair-3*. It gets the information of the room in which the first chair is found and it issues a command to move to that room, which corresponds to room-1. When asking again for a chair, Chair-2 is obtained, and it stays in room-2. With another query on Chair, Chair-3 is obtained and it issues the command to

Fig. 8 Test sequence with the CHAIR object

move to room-3, which corresponds with the last known chair. This behavior is visually described in figure 8.

If it is the case of unknown objects, when asked again for CHAIR after having discarded the chairs from the previous test, the operation sequence can be seen in figure 9.

At last, one more query on chair that can be seen in figure 8. In this case, it is necessary to explore for CHAIRS, searching in rooms where chairs could be present.

6.3 Unknown objects in unknown rooms

This test is carried out to ensure the correct operation in cases in which it has been introduced, as semantic target, a conceptual object and real object has not observed and that desired object is found in unidentified rooms. The object asked for is the WASHBASIN. In this case the system tries to find bathrooms, as is shown in figure 10.

6.4 Object search by characteristics

Based on the knowledge shown in figure 11, the system is asked for something to drink and the system deduced that it had to find a soft drink, coffee or fresh water. With this, the problem is reduced to the previous cases of searching

Fig. 9 Test sequence with the CHAIR object when there is no match with no observed physical object

Fig. 10 Test sequence with the WASHBASIN object

CONCEPTUAL OBJECT	UTILITY OBJECT	MEANING UTILITY	UTILITY CHARACTERISTIC OBJECT
WATER	DRINK SOFTDRINK	RELAXING REST	CLEAN HOT WATER
COFFEE	DRINK COFFEE		DRINK COLD WATER
SOFTDRINK	REST CHAIR		CLEAN COLD WATER
PRINTER			WATER COLD WATER
COMPUTER			CLEAN LUKEWARM WATER
CHAIR			WATER LUKEWARM WATER
CONCEPTUAL OBJECT ROOM	CHARACTERISTIC OBJECT	INTERACTION	
COMPUTER OFFICE	COLD WATER	PRINTER USED_WITH COMPUTER	
	LUKEWARM WATER		
	HOT WATER		
	HOT COFFEE		

Fig. 11 Knowledge of the robot represented on tables.

for an object (known or unknown). Later, a hot drink was requested and the system deduces that it must get coffee, being a case of search by object (coffee) already solved. With the knowledge shown in figure 11 and telling the system that something relaxing was searched for, the response was trying to find a chair.

6.5 Objects search by semantic proximity

Finally, with the knowledge shown in figure 11 and telling the system that a printer was needed, the system deduced that it must go to the office (in a home environment) to search for the computer because a printer may be found. For that, the system used the information of the relations between objects (computer-printer).

6.6 Unknown objects in known rooms

In this test the result of asking for conceptual objects that have not been observed but its location must be known, as it is inferred in the reasoning module, has been examined. It is checked that such inference is carried out and that the topological destination is right. It has been tried to ask for a HEATER. The system issues the command to go to all rooms with a heater. None of them were identified and it issued the action *explore*.

6.7 Unknown rooms

The system has been asked for a conceptual room that has no correspondence with a physical room because it has not been identified as a room. The room asked for was the BEDROOM. The system explores to search for the bedroom. As no room was identified as a bedroom in the database, the reasoning module returns the result that launches the explorer module looking for a bedroom.

6.8 Testing complete system

To test the system in a real scenario, a Turtlebot robot has been used. The robot includes a laptop to command it and to process the data from odometry

Fig. 12 Testing room

and from an ASUS Xtion Pro Live camera. A second laptop has been added to manage the semantic system developed in that work. To get the hardware and software integration, the proposed system is developed under the Robot Operating System (ROS), using C++ programming language.

Tests have been performed in a reserved area for teachers and researchers that includes three subareas: A reading area, a work area and a entertainment area. Figure 12 contains a schematic drawing of the environment.

To perform low level navigation tasks, a geometric representation of the environment have been used. A geometric map of the room has been build a priori, using the Gmapping ROS package that provides a laser-based SLAM (Simultaneous Localization and Mapping). Gmapping package generates geometric map of the environment and tools to plan and navigate in the map. The ASUS Xtion Pro Live camera has been configured as a laser-based sensor, using pointcloud-to-laserscan ROS package. The geometric map of the working environment is shown in figure 13.

The software architecture developed under ROS contains object environment detection modules, that includes object recognition [12], perception of artificial landmarks sourced by Ar-ToolKit [11] and simulated perception, but in this test a geometric location of the objects has been include in the map and in the tables of the database.

The system is completed with a robot-user interaction module with speech recognition and speech generation [28] that is used to ask the user for the target and to ask for information when database has not several options or not enough information.

In the test, the robot received the request to go to a *fun* place and a query is required to the system. Then the system proceed to seek alternatives. The first route taken by the robot is marked with a red colour rectangle in Figure 12. This corresponds to the search path of the television, because the robot had the relation between *TV watching* and *fun* in its database. The robot had the knowledge of the existence of the objects in the area labeled as *entertainment area* and the coordinates of the objects, so the robot moves to the TV position (Figure 14), using the coordinates of the TV from the database.

Fig. 13 Geometric map of the testing room.

Fig. 14 Final position of the robot path: in front of the TV.

When the robot asks the user if it is the desired destination, the user answers negatively (user does not want to watch television). Then, a second query is required to the system which led the robot to the final position of the book stand of figure 12. The reading area is selected, because the inference system associated *read* with *fun*, and although it had no book object in the database, it had labeled that area as reading area and it was the best place to find a book, since the database relates *book* with *book stand*, and *book stand* with *reading area*. Then, the robot moves to the reading area position (Figure 15), using the coordinates of the reading area from the database.

Fig. 15 Final position of the robot path: in the reading area.

Several test were performed, doing different queries types. When the robot had not enough information to reach the target, it asked the user to complete the information in the database an get the destination. The test discussed above and how the robot acquires new information asking the user, is shown in the video hosted on https://youtu.be/mhW_undRMgQ

6.9 Analysis system efficiency

These experiments also allowed to make some comments on the to discuss the efficiency of the proposed system under certain circumstances. These tests were performed assuming the system has the information in Tables 1, 2, 3 and Figure 11.

6.9.1 System recursiveness

The efficiency of the system has not been changed in situations that required to perform multiple recursive calls. This recursion is manifested in calls to the function of obtaining destination whose pseudocode is the algorithm 1. That function calls a number of functions going back to call themselves or to the same initial function. All calls to this function are discussed below to find out if recursion could be a problem. We conducted a test of basic search for a conceptual room. The relevant time data that can be affected by the recursion are shown in Table 4. In this first test we have order to find the office and there is no recursion, data are a reference for the next test. The second test requires three levels of recursion. It consist in asking the system to find a sheet of paper. For this we have added a new interaction information that relates objects *SHEET OF PAPER* with *PRINTER* by *IS _USED _WITH* relationship. The results are shown in Table 5.

Requested destination: OFFICE				
Iteration	Method	Target Request	Response	Time
1	getPhysicalRoomFromConceptualRoom	OFFICE	Room-2	6 ms
Total time for calculoDestino (this may include other non-recursive methods)				10 ms

Table 4 Runtimes results for a call that does not need recursion.

Requested destination: SHEET OF PAPER				
Iteration	Method	Target Request	Response	Time
1	searchForAnObject	SHEET_PAPER	PRINTER	8 ms
2	searchForAnObject	PRINTER	COMPUTER	8 ms
3	searchForAnObject	COMPUTER	OFFICE	7 ms
1	getPhysicalRoomFromConceptualRoom	OFFICE	Room-2	6 ms
Total time for calculoDestino (this may include other non-recursive methods)				36 ms

Table 5 Runtime results for a call that causes several recursive calls.

Requested destination: A FUNNY PLACE				
Iteration	Method	Target Request	Response	Time
1	searchForMeaning	FUNNY	BOOK/T.V.	9 ms
1	searchForAnObject	BOOK	READING_AREA	3 ms
1	getPhysicalRoomFromConceptualRoom	READING_AREA	Position	8 ms
Total time for calculoDestino (this may include other non-recursive methods)				34 ms

Table 6 Runtime results for a call that causes several recursive calls. It is the same call in the test in section 6.8.

We have also done the same analysis with searches of the experiments section 6.8 and the result is shown in Table 6. This comparison shows that the system allows and handles competently recursion because runtimes grow normally.

6.9.2 Processing time in larger environments

The procesing times do not increase too much when the database contains more information. Also, no problem was appreciated. This means that the system responds equally to larger and more detailed environments. We have taken relevant processing time data in the environment of the experiment section 6.8. Later we introduced more data to several tables and repeated the same sequence of the experiment. The comparison is showed in the table 7. The four most important functions that get information from the database of the iterations of the mentioned example have been chosen for the study. Function 1 is called to find objects that are related with *funny* utilities. The answer is *book* (because reading is funny) and *T.V.* (Because watching TV is funny). Processing time when there are 10 records in the relevant table of the database is very similar to when there are 55 records. Function 2 is called to find the location of the *book* object and concludes that it is in the *reading area*. Then the system queries using the 3 function which of the physical areas of the environment corresponds to the reading room and the position of this area

ID	Function with query	Size	Timing	Size	Timing
1	searchForMeaning	10	9 ms	55	11 ms
2	searchForObject	35	3 ms	115	3 ms
3	getPhysicalRoomFromConceptualRoom	3	8 ms	99	8 ms
Total time			20 ms		22 ms

Table 7 Results of runtimes with a call that makes several calls within the experiment of section 6.8.

is the destination toward which moves the robot. The increase in processing time for this information when there is considerably more records is negligible.

7 Conclusion

The interaction of robots with humans and their environments is a growing fact. In robotics there is a trend to adopt models with human inspiration capabilities, including the imitation of human abstraction levels and knowledge representation and reasoning capabilities. Among these abilities, the power to think symbolically, to extract semantic information from the environment and to reason with it to plan their actions is a goal to reach in the robotic field. This goal requires the use of cognitive architectures with the high abstraction level like those provided by semantic models. Semantic information of the environment increases the autonomy of the robot because it helps the robot to find solutions to a problem managing high level abstraction information.

This work proposed a representation of the environment using semantic information applied to robot navigation tasks. It has also been described that an efficient option to model the environment is the use of relational models, which includes decision rules in the relational information. The implementation using a database has been shown as a practical and efficient way to manage the information of the semantic model.

The proposed design enables the combination of different types of categorization of objects and rooms, working both with conceptual concepts and physical concepts. The manage of semantic knowledge is more flexible and adaptable than those proposed in other works, where changes are required in semantics and in the rules, when adding new objects in the conceptual hierarchy. The system contemplates some mechanism that allows to manage uncertainty allowing multiple categorization for objects.

The semantic system has been integrated in a robot architecture and tested in a robot working in an indoor environment. Results show the capability to reach targets using semantic information from the user that allows a more natural interaction between the human and the robot.

Having decoupled system modules allows us to test the navigation system with different cognitive architectures and choose the one that best suits the needs of each particular case. The reasoning module uses a reasoning class that implements an interface to ensure that covers the needs of the reasoning

module. A future work is to test the system with another reasoning class that implements the same interface but uses a different technology as could be Soar.

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